

ENGLISH INSTRUCTION THROUGH MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING AND ITS EFFECTS TO STUDENTS' ACADEMIC MOTIVATION

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ABSTRACT

The coronavirus disease outbreak has greatly affected the educational system, forcing it to shift to modular distance learning (MDL). Thus, students are forced to continue their education at home with the use of self-learning modules (SLMs). This paper attempts to investigate the perception of 231 students from Abundio Agarpao Sr. Memorial High School towards English instruction on MDL and its effect on the learner's academic motivation. The researcher utilized the descriptive-correlational method; used a validated questionnaire; and employed weighted mean, Spearman rank correlation coefficient, and Mann-Whitney U Test. Based on the statistical analysis, the findings revealed that there is generally a Very High students' perception of English instruction as regards MDL. Similarly, a Very High extent of academic motivation was recorded. Moreover a significant and strong relationship between the student's perceptions towards MDL and academic motivation was recorded. Family income was found to influence the student's perception towards MDL but did not affect their academic motivation. Proponent recommends using various motivational strategies to increase students' interest and engagement as well as improve educational policies to accommodate the issues experienced by constituents from low-income households.

Keywords: *Academic Motivation, Modular Distance Learning, English Instruction*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has altered daily life, presenting unparalleled public health, political, economic, social, and educational challenges. Educational programs all over the world have been impacted by home confinement and temporary school closures (Reimers and Schleicher, 2020; World Bank Group, 2020). Moreso, educational stakeholders have been affected by the complete transition to distance learning due to physical constraints brought about by this health crisis (Cachón-Zagalaz et al., 2020; Hiraoka & Tomoda, 2020). In order for teachers and students to carry on learning, the United Nations Education Science and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has appealed to governments to have maximized access to distance learning.

The new normal has led to a paradigm shift in the mode of instructional delivery in the education sector as a means to adapt to the country's current situation (Tria, 2020). The Philippines has made efforts toward developing the skills and expertise of educators and involved stakeholders to facilitate faster progress in this new type of educational setup (Hernando-Malipot, 2020; Guiamalon, et al., 2021).

In connection to this, the Department of Education has introduced a new method of instruction, Modular Distance Learning, where essential learning competencies are addressed through individualized instruction or Self-Learning Modules or SLMs (Anzaldo, 2021). Moreover, to allow schools to implement interventions for bridging learning gaps and ensuring learning continuity through K-12 with multiple learning delivery modalities, DepEd Order No. 012 S 2020: "Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for SY 2020-2021 in light of the COVID 19 Public Health Emergency" was implemented (DepEd, 2020).

Modular Distance Learning allows more inclusive access to education for students from rural areas and marginalized families (Agaton & Cueto, 2021). However, issues regarding learning content, comprehension, and student engagement have been raised in cases of language teachers during this shift to flexible learning (Tarrayo et al., 2021). On the other hand for students, their learning environment at home was linked to the greatest challenges in their learning (Barrot et al., 2021).

The sudden change of the educational delivery may set forth students a tough way to keep track of their academic motivation. In contrast, a series of studies seek to point out students' learning habits during this pandemic (Trung et al., 2020; Smith et al., 2021), no statistics can prove that the pandemic and some precautionary measures influence the academic motivation and learning of students in different countries.

Although there have been various studies that investigated the different issues experienced by educational stakeholders during this pandemic, there is still limited information available regarding students' perception of Modular Distance Learning and how it affects their motivation towards learning. Thus, the main goal of this study is to look into how Modular Distance Learning affects students' academic motivation in Philippine public secondary schools. This research also aims to determine the methods and

strategies used by educational institutions and the government in assisting students, parents, and teachers who are struggling with this new learning mode.

Research Questions

This study seeks to determine English Instruction Through Modular Distance Learning and its Effects to Students' Academic Motivation during the school year 2020-2021.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following sub-problems.

1. What is the perception of the students as regards to modular distance learning in terms of:
 - 1.1 teaching-learning process;
 - a. content;
 - b. instructional practice?
 - 1.2 assessment;
 - a. encourage time and effort on task;
 - b. facilitate the development of self-assessment and reflection on learning;
 - c. performance feedback?
 - 1.3 learner's support;
 - a. support from teachers;
 - b. support from parents?
 2. What is the extent of students' academic motivation?
 3. Is there a significant relationship between students' perception as regards to modular distance learning and their academic motivation?
 4. Is there a significant difference in students' perception as regards to modular distance learning when grouped according to their profile in terms of:
 - 4.1 family income; and
 - 4.2 sex?
 5. Is there a significant difference in students' academic motivation when grouped according to their profile?
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METHODOLOGY

Research design. The research utilized the descriptive correlational design to describe the perception of students towards Teachers' English Instruction on Modular Distance Learning and its effect on students' motivation. On the other hand, it will be correlational because the mentioned variables will be correlated.

Research environment. The locale of this study is in Bayawan City, also known as "The City of Character" specifically in Barangay Narra, Sitio Gamao, Negros Oriental, 6221, Philippines. The study was participated by students from Abundio Agarpao Sr. Memorial High School. Gamao is a sitio of Barangay Narra, situated 23 kilometers away from the heart of Bayawan City, it has electricity and a potable water supply. It has a

complete set of elected barangay officials under the leadership of Barangay Captain Hon. Nicolas D. Aragon and barangay councilors are working for the improvement of the community.

Gamao High School, now Abundio Agarpao Sr. Memorial High School, is a newly established school in Gamao, Narra Bayawan City, and the second high school in Barangay Narra with a school site occupying a lot of 10, 000 square meters, donated by the heirs of the late Abundio Agarpao Sr . The school has 16 faculty and staff. Abundio Agarpao Sr. Memorial High School consists of 230 males and 304 girls with a total of 534 enrolment as of February 2021.

Research respondents. The respondents of the study are the students of Abundio Agarpao Sr. Memorial High School with 230 males and 304 females or a total of 534 enrolment as of February 2021. A total of 231 were sampled as respondents. The students were chosen using the systematic random sampling method in which every second student in the list is part of the study.

The following is the distribution of the students:

Grade Level	Population	No. of Sampled Students
Grade 7	180	57
Grade 8	114	49
Grade 9	112	48
Grade 10	84	36
Grade 11	50	22
Grade 12	44	19
Total	534	231

Research instrument. A researcher-made questionnaire was used in this study. The researcher used the questions that were developed for this study. The questions were based on the feedback received from each of the listed problems. The first part of the study included data collected from the questionnaire based on the students' perception towards English instruction in MDL and their perceived academic motivations. This part addresses the issues on the teaching-learning process, assessment, and learner's support as perceived by students and their influence on academic motivation. The second part included analyzing the data based on students' profiles or demographics, specifically sex and family income, and how these affect their perception of English instruction and academic motivation.

To ensure content validity, the entire questionnaire was presented to three experts in the field of English. The prepared questions were checked to see if they were compatible with the study's basic problems. The recommendations of the experts were taken into consideration in revising and finalizing the questionnaire used in this study. To ensure reliability, a dry run was conducted. Thirty students were asked to participate. The Cronbach's alpha test was used to determine the questionnaire's reliability. This was measured to ensure the questionnaire's internal accuracy and reliability. It is a measure of the extent to which all the variables in the scale are positively related to each other and

its theoretical value varies from 0 to 1. Higher values of alpha are more desirable and a value of 0.70 is considered acceptable.

The reliability coefficients after the dry run are the following:

- (a) content: 0.834;
- (b) instructional practice: 0.935;
- (c) encourage time and effort in class: 0.800;
- (d) facilitate the development of self-assessment and reflection on learning: 0.923;
- (e) performance feedback: 0.924;
- (f) support from teachers: 0.863
- (g) support from parents: 0.916
- (h) support from peers: 0.629 – rejected; reliability <0.70
- (i) academic motivation:0.917

The following tools were used by the researcher in analyzing the data :

Weighted mean. This was used in getting the extent of students' perception of their (a) Teaching-Learning Process: Content and Instructional Practice, (b) Assessment: Encouragement on time and effort on tasks; facilitation of the development of self-assessment and reflection on learning; and performance feedback, and (c) Learner's Support: Parent's and Teacher's Support.

Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient. This was utilized to identify the degree of relationship between the students' perception towards teachers' English instruction in modular distance learning and their academic motivation. The test was selected since the data were on an ordinal scale.

Mann-Whitney U Test. This was used in identifying the significant difference in the students' perception towards teachers' English instruction in MDL and extent in academic motivation when grouped according to their profile in terms of family income and sex. The test was utilized since the data were on ordinal scale.

Scope of the study. This study focuses on determining the extent of students' perception on Teachers' English Instruction through modular distance learning and its relationship with students' academic motivation. The respondents of this study are the Junior and Senior High School students of Abundio Agarpao Sr. Memorial High School, Bayawan City Division.

Limitations of the study. In this study, students' perception of modular learning is limited to their views on the teaching-learning process, assessment, and learner's support. Additionally, the influence of students' demographics (sex and family income) on their perception of English instruction in the MDL setup was also analyzed. Other variables that may have affected the respondent's answers that were beyond the proponent's control, e.g. physical, emotional, and mental state, are considered as limitations in the study. These limitations are also applicable to the measurement of the student's extent of academic motivation.

This study is limited to the Grade 7 to Grade 12 students of Abundio Agarpao Sr. Memorial High School. Any variable differences in the quality of English modules between grade levels are not measured and are also treated as a limitation of the study. This study did not include specific perceptions of students in different grade levels as students were treated as a homogenous group. Thus, any conclusion is limited to the perception of Abundio Agarpao Sr. Memorial High School's students as a whole and not as separate grade levels.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 *Perception of the Students as Regards Modular Distance Learning in Terms of Teaching-Learning Process (n = 231)*

Teaching-Learning Process		w \bar{x}	VD	EoP
Content				
In the formulation of content, the teacher...				
1.	selects meaningful content that meets the needs of students.	6.54	SA	VH
2.	gives practice exercises that encourage the integration of learned concepts to real-life settings.	6.41	SA	VH
3.	formulates additional activities in the form of learning worksheets.	6.31	SA	VH
4.	devises differentiated activities based on students' multiple intelligences, learning styles, and readiness levels.	6.28	SA	VH
5.	uses various motivational strategies (i.e., advance organizers, puzzles, games) to hook the students' interest and engagement.	6.08	A	H
Composite		6.32	SA	VH
Instructional practice				
The English instruction, the teacher...				
1.	provides instructions in written works, performance tasks, and practice exercises.	6.45	SA	VH
2.	constantly monitors students' academic engagement and learning progress.	6.32	SA	VH
3.	frequently reminds students of the execution and completion of given activities in the SLM.	6.30	SA	VH
4.	logically develop lessons/activities as part of the instructional elements.	6.26	SA	VH
5.	immediately responds to students' queries related to learning content and engagements.	6.23	SA	VH
Composite		6.31	SA	VH
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Perception (EoP)		
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)		
5.29 – 6.14	Agree (A)	High (H)		
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree (SoA)	Somewhat High (SoH)		
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree/Disagree (NAD)	Moderate		
2.17 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree (SoD)	Somewhat Low (SoL)		
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree (D)	Low (L)		
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low		

Table 1.2 *Perception of the Students as Regards Modular Distance Learning in Terms of Assessment (n = 231)*

Assessment	w \bar{x}	VD	EoP
a. Encourage Time And Effort On Task			
The teacher...			
1. provides content and assessment that is logically organized and arranged from simple to complex, observable to abstract, etc.	6.44	SA	VH
2. allows me to seek help and assistance in doing assigned tasks.	6.39	SA	VH
3. devises instructional design that contributes to the timely attainment of learning tasks.	6.29	SA	VH
4. sets specific objectives and attainable goals in the given tasks to be completed in the assigned time period.	6.28	SA	VH
5. applies self-directed techniques, learning tasks, and formative assessments.	6.26	SA	VH
Composite	6.33	SA	VH
b. Facilitate The Development Of Self-Assessment And Reflection On Learning			
The teacher...			
1. sets criteria or rubrics that serve as guides on the execution of performance tasks.	6.45	SA	VH
2. prepares instructional activities that are intellectually-stimulating and develops my higher-order thinking skills.	6.39	SA	VH
3. gives assessment activities that ensure my active engagement as a learner.	6.33	SA	VH
4. formulates assessments that are aligned with specific objectives and learning contents.	6.32	SA	VH
5. enables me to apply self-directed techniques to develop my metacognitive skills and foster independent learning.	6.22	SA	VH
Composite	6.34	SA	VH
c. Performance Feedback			
The teacher...			
1. provides regular learning feedback to students through written notes	6.33	SA	VH
2. delivers accurate information on students' scores and grades.	6.33	SA	VH
3. establishes structures and systems through worksheets and performance task with rubrics.	6.30	SA	VH
4. gives constant updates through communicating with parents.	6.26	SA	VH
5. creates feedback routines on student learning.	6.26	SA	VH
Composite	6.30	SA	VH
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Perception (EoP)	
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)	
5.29 – 6.14	Agree (A)	High (H)	
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree (SoA)	Somewhat High (SoH)	
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree/Disagree (NAD)	Moderate	
2.17 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree (SoD)	Somewhat Low (SoL)	
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree (D)	Low (L)	
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low	

Table 1.3 Perception of the Students as Regards Modular Distance Learning in Terms of Learners' Support (n = 231)

Learner's support	w \bar{x}	VD	EoP
Support from Teachers:			
The teacher...			
1. strongly encourages my parent or guardian to monitor my learning progress and developments.	6.36	SA	VH
2. willingly or openly answers my parent's queries related to my academic engagements.	6.23	SA	VH
3. regularly conducts quarterly orientation and timely delivers reports on my learning progress.	6.22	SA	VH
4. constantly contacts my parent or guardian to inform and follow-up my instructional engagements.	6.22	SA	VH
5. evidently provides activities that involve my family's participation and encourage their assistance on given tasks.	6.12	A	H
Composite	6.23	SA	VH
Support from Parents:			
The parents/guardians...			
1. regularly attends meetings set by my teacher for updates on my academic standing	6.44	SA	VH
2. frequently checks and reviews if I finish all given activities in the SLM before submitting it to the teacher.	6.35	SA	VH
3. directly communicates with my teacher with regards to my school undertakings.	6.34	SA	VH
4. constantly asks my teacher if I miss any given activity.	6.31	SA	VH
5. timely gets and returns my module on weekly basis.	6.29	SA	VH
Composite	6.35	SA	VH
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Perception (EoP)	
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)	
5.29 – 6.14	Agree (A)	High (H)	
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree (SoA)	Somewhat High (SoH)	
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree/Disagree (NAD)	Moderate	
2.17 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree (SoD)	Somewhat Low (SoL)	
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree (D)	Low (L)	
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low	

Table 1.4 Summary Table on the Extent of Perception of the Students as Regards Modular Distance Learning (n = 231)

Variables	w \bar{x}	Extent of Perception
Teaching-Learning Process		
Content	6.32	Very High
Instructional Practice	6.31	Very High
Composite	6.32	Very High

Assessment

Encourage Time & Effort on Task	6.33	Very High
Facilitate the Development of Self-Assessment and Reflection on Learning	6.34	Very High
Performance Feedback	6.30	Very High
Composite	6.32	Very High

Learner's Support

Support From Teachers;	6.23	Very High
Support From Parents?	6.35	Very High
Composite	6.29	Very High

Legend: Scale	Extent of Perception (EoP)
6.15 – 7.00	Very High (VH)
5.29 – 6.14	High (H)
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat High (SoH)
3.57 – 4.42	Moderate
2.17 – 3.56	Somewhat Low (SoL)
1.85 – 2.70	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.84	Very Low

Table 2. *Extent of Student's Academic Motivation*

In doing my modules, I...	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoM
1. comply all given activities, written works, and performance tasks as part of the SLM's lesson content.	6.30	SA	VH
2. feel excitement in getting and returning my module in every posted schedule. .	6.29	SA	VH
3. put premium importance in getting high marks on my completed tasks and assignments.	6.26	SA	VH
4. exert maximum effort to achieve desirable learning outcomes and results.	6.25	SA	VH
5. feel happiness in doing written works and other variety of instructional activities.	6.23	SA	VH
6. enjoy intellectual challenge in doing academic tasks and activities reflected in the SLM.	6.23	SA	VH
7. formulate self-reflective questions to further my understanding on learning content and concepts	6.19	SA	VH
8. engage in thought provoking and intellectually stimulating activities and assessment exercises.	6.18	SA	VH
9. feel satisfied with instructional activities that enable me to track my progress and mastery of the target competencies.	6.18	SA	VH
10. demonstrate satisfaction in the completion of every assigned task in the module.	6.13	A	H

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Motivation (EoM)
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
5.29 – 6.14	Agree (A)	High (H)
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree (SoA)	Somewhat High (SoH)
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree/Disagree (NAD)	Moderate
2.17 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree (SoD)	Somewhat Low (SoL)
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low

Table 3. Relationships between Students' Perception as Regards Modular Distance Learning and Their Academic Motivation (n = 231)

Variables Correlated to Students' Motivation	r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Teaching-Learning Process				
Content	0.656	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Instructional Practice	0.647	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Overall	0.623	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Assessment				
Encourage Time & Effort on Task	0.703	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Facilitate the Development of Self-Assessment and Reflection on Learning	0.707	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Performance Feedback	0.719	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Overall	0.775	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Learner's Support				
Support From Teachers;	0.759	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Support From Parents?	0.750	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Overall	0.750	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Legend:	Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
Between	± 0.50 to ± 1.00	± strong relationship
Between	± 0.30 to ± 0.49	± moderate relationship
Between	± 0.10 to ± 0.29	± weak relationship
Between	± 0.01 to ± 0.09	± very weak relationship

Table 4. Analysis Table on the Difference in Students' Perception as Regards Modular Distance Learning when grouped according to Their Profile

Variables	N	Median	Mean Rank	U	p-value	Decision	Remark
Family Income							
Less than 5,000	166	6.39	109	4,232	0.011	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
5,000 and greater	65	6.49	134				
Sex							
Male	93	6.42	119	6,162	0.610	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Female	138	6.39	114				

Mann-Whitney U Test at 0.05 level of significance

Table 5. Analysis Table on the Difference in Students' Academic Motivation when grouped according to Their Profile

Variables	N	Median	Mean Rank	U	p-value	Decision	Remark
Family Income							
Less than 5,000	166	6.30	112	4,707	0.131	Fail to reject H ₀₃	Not significant
5,000 & greater	65	6.40	127				
Sex							
Male	93	6.30	116	6,382	0.944	Fail to reject H ₀₃	Not significant
Female	138	6.30	116				

Mann-Whitney U Test at 0.05 level of significance

DISCUSSION

Table 1.1 presents the data on the perception of the students on modular distance learning in terms of the Teaching-Learning process which includes Content and Instructional Practice. The results reveal that the extent of students' perception of the Content is Very High for items 1-4 as evidenced in the weighted mean with values ranging from 6.28 to 6.54. On the other hand, a High extent of perception was found for item 5 (use of various motivational strategies) with a weighted mean of 6.08. Therefore, it can be deduced that in the formulation of the content of the English modules, the teacher was able to select meaningful content that met the needs of students and gave tasks that encouraged learning. This is in line with the work of Williams & Williams (2011), where they suggest that the content of instructional materials should not only be accurate and

timely but also relevant and useful to the lives of the students. This is also discussed by Simonson et al. (2011) as they claim that correct instructional design that applies research-based principles towards educational practice is essential towards effective distance education. Teachers need to consider a lot of motivational factors when designing supplemental learning resources (Jimenez, 2020).

Furthermore, it was claimed that diverse distance learning activities stimulate student motivation and lead to self-learning (Lassoued et al., 2020). Rapanta et al. (2020) also suggest that activities that are based on a mix of different design approaches, which met the readiness levels of students and are based on authentic contexts, should be considered for distance learning to increase student engagement. Thus, these efforts could be done to increase the extent of perception for item 5.

Similarly, in terms of Instructional Practice, the data revealed that students' perception is Very High with weighted mean values ranging from 6.23 to 6.45 and an overall composite weighted mean of 6.31. This indicates that the students found that in terms of teaching instruction, the teacher was able to provide instructions for tasks, monitor them in the completion and progress of their activities, and immediately respond to their queries. A study by Filippello et al. (2019) has shown how learning activities that promote consideration of students' perspectives and inputs delivered the greatest effectiveness when it comes to encouraging mastery and persistence among students.

In summary, these findings on the Teaching-Learning process are in agreement with Martin (2020), when he claimed that high-quality instruction and content is needed to reduce the problem associated with poor impulse control, like the abandonment of schoolwork for gaming or social messaging, among students and keep learners engaged and on track with their tasks.

Table 1.2 presents the data on the perception of the students on modular distance learning in terms of Assessment which includes the teacher's (a) encouragement on spending time and effort on tasks;(b) guidance on student's self-assessment and reflection on learning, and (c) performance feedback.

In terms of encouraging time and effort on tasks, the data reveal that Very High perception is present with the weighted mean values ranging from 6.26 to 6.44 and a composite weighted mean of 6.33. This means that the teacher provides content and assessment that are logically organized and devised an instructional design that contributes to the timely attainment of tasks. Moreover, it also indicates how the teacher has effectively set attainable goals within specific timeframes. This conclusion matches the findings of Martin (2020) who asserts that lessons need to be clear and well structured, and at the same time, delivered in manageable chunks such that students will have enough time to do the tasks and for teachers to give timely feedback. In terms of devising instructional designs that are attainable, Cahapay (2020) has proposed three considerations in determining the essential contents for learning which she enumerates as significance, relevance, and utility.

Furthermore, in the area of facilitating the development of self-assessment and reflection on learning it is indicated that perception is also Very High with weighted mean

values ranging from 6.22 to 6.45 and a composite weighted mean of 6.34. This indicates that the teacher was able to effectively prepare instructional activities and formulate assessments that encouraged the development of autonomy or self-direction and fosters independent learning. This is affirmed by Filippello et al. (2019) whose study argues that learning activities should be structured in a way wherein it fosters autonomy and self-regulation through the consideration of student's perspectives and the addition of support elements that encourage self-initiation and management. Similarly, Dickhauser et al. (2011), asserts that the autonomy-support of teachers which encourages choice and self-initiation can develop a positive attitude towards academic tasks and problem-solving strategies when facing obstacles.

Item 1 has the highest weighted mean of 6.45. This shows how the respondents value set criteria or rubrics as guides in the execution of tasks. This is in correspondence to the suggestion of Rapanta et al (2020) that self-regulation should be a part of the assessment. They explain that the self-paced, asynchronous activities with the clear indicated assessment process for participation, like self-reflections or portfolios, are good means for students to account for the time and effort they need to adapt to the new learning situation.

On the other hand, the area in terms of performance feedback has a rating of Very High with weighted means values ranging from 6.26 to 6.33 with a composite weighted mean of 6.30. It can be deduced that the teacher was able to provide regular learning feedback and deliver accurate information on students' scores and grades. Moreso, this is indicative of established feedback routines on student learning and constant communication of updates through parents. Costello and Crane (2013) encourage actions towards increasing the impact of feedback in a positive and efficient manner as learner-centered feedback is an important component of the learning process. Funa & Talaue (2021) also established the importance of assessment and evaluation in modules towards the development of independence and responsibility towards one's own learning through the provision of opportunities to learners to express and develop new understandings.

Table 1.3 shows the perception of students to Modular Distance Learning as regards the support they get from their parents and teachers. Generally, Very High perception of Teacher's support is observed from item 1 to 4 as weighted mean values range from 6.22 to 6.36 and a composite weighted mean of 6.23. This means that teachers manifested positive responses and willingness towards inquiries and clarifications related to the topics or lessons. Engagement with parents was also done in relation to learning procedures and feedback. Item 5 has the lowest weighted mean with 6.12 and is also the only item rated as High in the perception index.

These findings are in correspondence with the results of the study done by Funa and Talaue (2021) wherein they acknowledged the efforts of teachers to mitigate the consequences of inequalities among students through the provision of alternative activities, deadline adjustments, the opening of various communication and support channels, and requesting assistance from parents with regards to their children's workload. These extensions and accommodations made by teachers have become vital

to distance education in the time of this pandemic. Similarly, Castroverde & Alcala (2021) recognized the initiatives done by teachers to cope with the challenges brought by modular distance modality. They characterized this in the way teachers have innovated teaching strategies that adapt to changes brought about by the new normal trend in education, being flexible and optimistic, and through their provision of alternative plans in the learning process.

Similarly, the student's extent of perception on modular distance learning as regards to Parent's support is also Very High. The weighted mean values for it ranged from 6.29 to 6.44 and a composite weighted mean of 6.35. These findings indicate how parents played an important role in correspondence with teachers regarding academic standing, performance, and updates.

Moreover, parent's support receiving a higher composite weighted mean of 6.35 when compared to teacher's support (6.23). This coincides with how Tus (2021) and Djafar et al. (2021) claims that parents have taken the forefront and a more active role in the child's education. This is also indicative of the parent's fulfilment of their roles in making sure that their children are doing their tasks and proactive measures have been made by them to accommodate learning at home. Additionally, this is also in correspondence to the publication of Mora and Escardibul (2016) which indicates that the environment at home influences the tendency of parents to participate in student's education at home which in turn affects the academic success of the child.

Overall, very high learner's support will have a positive influence on the student's perceived academic motivation. As suggested by the Self-Determination Theory, support from significant adults, such as parents and teachers, is essential for a student's well-being (Ryan & Deci, 2017).

Table 1.4 summarizes the student's extent of perception as regards to modular distance learning in terms of (a) teaching-learning process, (b) assessment, and (c) learner's support. The results present that students' perception in all the identified areas of modular distance learning is very high with the following composite means: (a) content: 6.32; (b) assessment: 6.32, and (c) learner's support: 6.29. The very high perception of students on all variables indicates active and successful execution of learning-teaching practice and assessment by teachers who prepare the modules and by parents who bear high responsibility in supervising academic completion of work and tasks at home. Additionally, this also means that students are comfortable in modular distance learning and have great autonomy and self-direction which can mitigate issues brought by the context of distance learning. Simonson et al. (2011) affirm this with their reports that well-designed courses produce more positive learning outcomes and are influential to overall student satisfaction.

Moreover, this is in correspondence to the claims by Wei and Chou (2020) that learners' perceptions of self-efficacy in distance learning are affected by their learning readiness. Learners with a high level of self-efficacy toward online learning performed better than those with low levels of self-efficacy.

Table 2 shows the data on students' extent of academic motivation as regards to Modular distance learning. Generally, the extent of motivation is Very High given that the weighted mean values for items 1-9 range from 6.18 to 6.30, and the composite mean is at 6.22. Item 10, which characterizes satisfaction in the completion of every assigned task in the module is rated High with a weighted mean of 6.13. This level of motivation is rooted on the student's (a) goal of complying all required activities and written works; (b) interest in getting high marks; (c) enjoyment in doing written works and other activities. Moreover, the data also indicates that the modules allowed them to track their progress and mastery, and exert maximum effort to achieve their target competencies. This result is affirmed by the study done by Tipon et al. (2021) where they also found out that senior high school motivation towards distance learning is high.

Furthermore, these findings are in line with the work of Williams & Williams (2011), where they specified that student motivation is impacted by five key ingredients which include the student (one that has access, ability and interest in education), teacher (well-trained, dedicated, and responsive to their students), content (accurate, timely, and stimulating), method/process (inventive, encouraging, and beneficial), and environment (accessible, safe, positive, and personalized). They also claim that the extent of learning is dependent on the extent of motivation.

Table 3 presents the data in identifying the relationship between the students' perception as regards to modular distance learning and their academic motivation. As shown, all paired variables have computed r -values that are greater than 0.50 and all p -values (0.000) are less than the level of significance (0.05). These findings allow rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that a strong and significant relationship exists between the following: (a) teaching-learning activities and academic motivation; (b) assessment and academic motivation; and (c) learners' support and academic motivation. This also implies that the higher the teaching-learning activities, assessment, and learners' support that the students perceive, the higher also is their academic motivation.

Sison et al. (2021) affirms these results in their study where they found a significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic motivation. Moreover, this further asserts their claim that having good self-efficacy can motivate students to do well in school and increase their academic success. This is also in correspondence with Avila & Genio (2020) whose study shows that students can be motivated in distance learning through proper support, assistance, and encouragement.

High academic motivation, in this context, can be attributed to the presence of very high perception on all variables. Very high structure and dialogue has led to very high autonomy. This can be attributed to the fact that, despite having a high structure in the modular distance learning processes, teachers are required by DepEd Order No. 32 s. 2020: "Guidelines on the Engagement of Services of Learning Support Aides to Reinforce the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in Time of COVID-19 Pandemic" to frequently communicate to parents and learners on updates and feedback on their learning performance. Thus, the results do not necessarily go against Moore's transactional distance theory.

A study done by Tipon et al. (2021) also found a significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic motivation. This strong relationship between the Teaching-learning process, Assessment, and Learner's support as revealed in this study, is in correspondence to the study of Li et al. (2016), who suggests that as learners become more satisfied with teaching materials, assessment strategies, and workload they become more satisfied with the overall learning experience. Specifically, the high dialogue perception, which is supported by the strong relationship between academic motivation and support from teachers, is also supported by Cavus (2015) wherein he claims that it is less difficult for learners to ask questions to teachers individually and resolves the issue experienced in traditional learning setup. Moreover, Zeichner (2018) also agrees with the result that feedback results in better academic motivation.

This study has reaffirmed the shared responsibility of teachers and parents, in the context of this pandemic, on the learner's academic success as suggested by the significant relationship of learners' support towards their very high perception of modular distance learning. Gumapac et al. (2021) has conducted a study that reinforces this result, as they claim that parents have become highly engaged in sustaining motivation, coaching and tutoring, and monitoring the student's compliance data. Similarly, Tus (2021) also asserts that, despite not having a significant relationship, parental involvement, in terms of providing guidance and supervision in children's academic learning, is influential to their academic performance.

Table 4 reveals the data in analyzing the difference in the perceptions of the students as regards modular distance learning when they are grouped according to their profile. With regards to family income, it shows that the p-value (0.011) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This finding warrants rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that the perceptions of the students differ significantly. As seen in the data, students whose family income is 5,000 and greater have higher values of median and mean rank than those students from families earning less. This signifies further that students with higher family income have better perceptions about modular distance learning than those with lower family income. This is in agreement with the findings of Girik (2020) wherein despite the positive perception of students towards distance learning, financial issue experienced by students is identified as one of the commonly reported problems related to education during the pandemic.

Although environmental conditions of households and parents' literacy are not part of the variables in this study, the researcher can conclude that the economic situation clearly affects the perception of students with regard to modular distance learning. This is supported by many researchers who claim that socio-economic stressors negatively affected students from low-income families more, compared to their counterparts, when it comes to education during this pandemic. Rodriguez-Planaz (2020) has shown in her study that low-income students were generally more likely to be negatively-affected in their education in the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic brought about by challenges related to lack of internet, childcare responsibilities, health issues, and stress. Cleofas and Rocha (2020) also agrees with this claim, as they assert that students from low socioeconomic localities have higher mental distress due to their limited financial capacity to satisfy their

educational needs during this pandemic. Additionally, a study by Llamer (2021) also found that unfavorable outcomes resulted from the adverse economic impacts brought by the pandemic on parent's livelihoods, towards their childrens' perception of the new modes of learning.

Furthermore, as shown in Table 4, distance learning favors students with better economic status. Economic constraints can affect learners' perception of distance learning as financing of distance education is an obstacle parents have to face which includes purchasing technology in order to aid learning at home (Danchikov et al, 2021). Greater attention is needed for low-middle-income households with poor access to technology, food, health, and security in terms of policymaking in distance education to help alleviate from these demographic-specific issues (Agaton & Cueto, 2021).

The data also divulge that sex is not significantly related to their perception of modular distance learning ($p = 0.610 > \alpha = 0.05$). This suggests that the student's sex is not a factor in the perception of modular distance learning. Moreover, this is a good indicator that respondents had similar experiences towards modular distance learning and have the similar perceived extent of academic motivation regardless of sex. It also shows how the academic curriculum and English instructional practice were effective and reliable to students regardless of the mentioned demographic.

In summary, family income influenced the student's perception of modular distance learning and is not true when grouped according to sex. Engzell et.al (2020) affirms this with their baseline data showing that learning loss is more pronounced in students from disadvantaged homes and that they found little to no evidence that this effect differs in terms of sex. Therefore, efforts from both DepEd and other government bodies should be made to alleviate constituents gravely affected economically by this pandemic to improve this perception of students in low-income families on modular distance learning.

Table 5 reflects the data in analyzing the difference in the academic motivation of the students when they are grouped according to their profile. The data reveal that all p-values for family income ($p = 0.131$) and sex ($p = 0.944$) are greater than the level of significance (0.05). These figures will not warrant rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference in the academic motivation of the students when grouped according to their income and sex. This connotes that regardless of their financial status and sex, the students manifest the same level of academic motivation.

The lack of significant difference between these demographics towards learner's motivation is in correspondence to Li et al. (2016), wherein they claimed that despite the diversity of learners, underlying learning experiences are similar. The results indicate that effective teaching practice and the positive relationship between teachers and parents in the context of MDL have positively impacted students' motivation.

Summary of Findings

From the data gathered in the study, the following salient findings are hereby presented.

1. Student's Perception of Modular Distance Learning.

The data disclosed that students' perception on modular distance learning as regards to English learning and instruction in terms of the following areas are as follows:

1.1 teaching-learning process;

- a. content: $w\bar{x} = 6.32$ (Very High);
- b. instructional practice: $w\bar{x} = 6.31$ (Very High)

1.2 assessment;

- a. encourage time and effort on task: $w\bar{x} = 6.33$ (Very High);
- b. facilitate the development of self-assessment and reflection on learning: $w\bar{x} = 6.34$ (Very High);
- c. performance feedback: $w\bar{x} = 6.30$ (Very High);

1.3 learner's support;

- a. support from teachers: $w\bar{x} = 6.23$ (Very High); and
- b. support from parents: $w\bar{x} = 6.35$ (Very High)

2. Student's extent of academic motivation.

The results revealed that the student's extent of academic motivation was Very High ($w\bar{x} = 6.22$).

3. Relationship between Students' Perception as Regards to Modular Distance Learning and Their Academic Motivations

The data revealed that a significant and strong relationship existed between the academic motivation of students and the following variables:

Teaching-Learning Process

1.1 Content: $r_s = 0.656$; $p = 0.000$;

1.2 Instructional Practice: $r_s = 0.647$; $p = 0.000$;

overall; $r_s = 0.623$; $p = 0.000$

Assessment

1.3 encourage time and effort on task: $r_s = 0.703$; $p = 0.000$;

1.4 facilitate the development of self-assessment and reflection on learning: $r_s = 0.707$; $p = 0.000$;

1.5 performance feedback: $r_s = 0.719$; $p = 0.000$;

overall: $r_s = 0.775$; $p = 0.000$;

Learner's Support

1.6 support from teachers: $r_s = 0.759$; $p = 0.000$;

1.7 support from parents: $r_s = 0.750$; $p = 0.000$;

overall: $r_s = 0.750$; $p = 0.000$

4. Difference in Students' Perception as Regards Modular Distance Learning When Grouped According to their Profile

- 4.1 family income: p-value = 0.011 (Significant in favor of the higher income families)
- 4.2 sex: p-value = 0.610 (Not Significant)

5. Difference in Students' Academic Motivation When Grouped According to Their Profile.

- 1.1 family monthly income: p-value = 0.131 (Not Significant)
- 1.2 sex: p-value = 0.944 (Not Significant)

Conclusions

On the basis of the findings, the following conclusions are produced:

1. The student's perception as regards to modular distance learning in terms of the teaching-learning process, instructional practice, and assessment are very high.
2. The extent of students' academic motivation is very high.
3. There was a strong and significant relationship between students' perception as regards to modular distance learning and their academic motivation.
4. There was a significant difference in students' perception as regards to modular distance learning when students were grouped according to family income, while there was no significant difference when grouped by sex.
5. There was no significant difference between students' academic motivation and their profile.

In general, the perception of junior and senior high school students in Abundio Agarpao Sr. Memorial High School toward English instruction on MDL is generally Very High and the student's extent of academic motivation is Very High.

Recommendations

In line with the conclusions made, the proponent of this study would like to recommend the following:

1. Teachers should continue providing quality, effective SLMs and timely learning feedback and assessment as there is high significance between these and academic motivation.
2. Teachers should use various motivational strategies to increase students' interest and engagement as well as provide activities that involve family participation and assistance to improve parental support in student learning.
3. Teachers should be encouraged to give timely performance feedback and assessment to students through their parents.
4. Further research is needed to be done by teachers on the implications of economic standing towards students in this MDL setup.

5. There is a need to improve policies and procedures directed by DepEd in the context of MDL in order to accommodate and improve the experience of those students belonging to low-income households.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Throughout the study, the researcher demonstrated all relevant ethical considerations. Since humans were selected as research subjects, details were kept confidential. Respondent's integrity and privacy were also respected.

The researcher adopted the ethical guidelines set by Foundation University's Ethics Committee. Significant and ethically correct consultation was observed to ensure that the research subject is evidently sound. To escape censure, the researcher maintained a non-judgmental stance during the interview process. Furthermore, the participants were asked to sign a consent form indicating that they had a complete understanding of the study's risks and benefits.

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